

Supplementary materials for “An observational study of the relationships between time from calving to pregnancy, body condition score and lameness amongst dairy cows, utilizing video data”

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SUMMARY

This study analyzed data from four British dairy farms that used an automated video monitoring system (Agsenz; HerdVision) to measure body condition and mobility of cows. Taking into account farm effects and number of lactations, our analysis showed that cows in poor body condition at drying-off, those that lost body condition between drying-off and calving, which were in poor body condition at calving and that were lame had an increased number of days from calving to subsequent pregnancy. Automated systems offer cost-effective, repeatable, objective and labor-saving tools to enhance dairy cow health and productivity by early identification of at-risk animals.

Table S1: Schonfeld Residuals Tests for four Cox proportional hazard models estimating the associations between calving-pregnancy interval (CPI), BCS, and lameness adjusted for lactation number and farm.

	Chi-square	Degrees of Freedom	<i>P</i> -value
Model 1	1.01	3	<i>P</i> = 0.80
Model 2	4.57	3	<i>P</i> = 0.20
Model 3	2.03	3	<i>P</i> = 0.57
Model 4	2.99	3	<i>P</i> = 0.39

Table S2: Change in Log-Likelihood for four Cox proportional hazard models estimating the associations between calving-pregnancy interval (CPI), BCS, and lameness adjusted for lactation number and farm, as variables were added sequentially for each model from the NULL model, and significance tested through a Chi-square distribution with 1 degree of freedom.

	Parameter	Change in Log-Likelihood	<i>P</i> -value
Model 1	BCS1	0.68	<i>P</i> = 0.24
	Lactation Number	0.42	<i>P</i> = 0.36
	Lameness	10.72	<i>P</i> <0.001
Model 2	BCS2	4.65	<i>P</i> = 0.002
	Lactation Number	0.58	<i>P</i> = 0.28
	Lameness	16.42	<i>P</i> <0.001
Model 3	BCS2-BCS1	1.95	<i>P</i> = 0.048
	Lactation Number	0.36	<i>P</i> = 0.4
	Lameness	11.84	<i>P</i> <0.001
Model 4	dBCS	1	<i>P</i> = 0.16
	Lactation Number	0.02	<i>P</i> = 0.84
	Lameness	18.19	<i>P</i> <0.001

Table S3: Cox proportional hazard models to estimate the association between body condition score, lameness and calving-pregnancy interval (CPI) on four British dairy farms, with lactation number and Farm as fixed effects.

Model # (n)	Predictor Variable	HR ⁴ (95% ci)	P-value
1 (777)	BCS1 ¹	1.11 (0.8 - 1.54)	<i>P</i> = 0.53 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lame	0.64 (0.53 - 0.78)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm A	1.00	-
	Farm B	1.54 (1.3 - 1.83)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm C	4.04 (2.8 - 5.84)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm D	0.9 (0.68 - 1.19)	<i>P</i> = 0.48 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.01 (0.95 - 1.07)	<i>P</i> = 0.76 <i>ns</i> ⁵
2 (1425)	BCS2 ²	1.33 (1.1 - 1.61)	<i>P</i> = 0.003
	Lame	0.65 (0.56 - 0.76)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm A	1.00	-
	Farm B	1.57 (1.34 - 1.84)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm C	1.33 (1.15 - 1.53)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm D	0.89 (0.71 - 1.11)	<i>P</i> = 0.3 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.06 (1.02 - 1.11)	<i>P</i> = 0.006
3 (777)	(BCS2-BCS1)	1.72 (1.11 - 2.66)	<i>P</i> = 0.015
	Lame	0.63 (0.52 - 0.77)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm A	1.00	-
	Farm B	1.48 (1.25 - 1.76)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm C	3.77 (2.61 - 5.44)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm D	0.9 (0.68 - 1.18)	<i>P</i> = 0.43 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.01 (0.95 - 1.08)	<i>P</i> = 0.65 <i>ns</i> ⁵
4 (1425)	dBCS ³	1.29 (0.98 - 1.69)	<i>P</i> = 0.067
	Lame	0.64 (0.55 - 0.74)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm A	1.00	-
	Farm B	1.6 (1.36 - 1.88)	<0.001
	Farm C	1.3 (1.12 - 1.49)	<0.001
	Farm D	0.85 (0.68 - 1.06)	0.15 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.05 (1.01 - 1.09)	0.024

⁵ *ns* = not statistically significant

¹ BCS1 = BCS at drying-off

² BCS2 = BCS at calving

³ dBCS = maximum BCS loss between calving and pregnancy

⁴ HR = Hazard Ratio (95% confidence interval)

Table S4: Cox proportional hazard model to estimate the association between body condition score, BCS) lameness and calving-pregnancy interval (CPI) on four British dairy farms, with lactation number as a fixed effect and Farm as a random effect, including an interaction term between BCS and lactation number.

Model # (n)	Predictor Variable	HR ⁴ (95% ci)	P-value
1 (777)	BCS1 ¹	0.9 (0.48 - 1.66)	<i>P</i> = 0.73 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lactation Number (LN)	0.85 (0.46 - 1.56)	<i>P</i> = 0.59 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lame	0.65 (0.54 - 0.79)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm A	0.57 (0.26 - 1.25)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm B	0.86 (0.39 - 1.88)	
	Farm C	2.07 (0.95 - 4.52)	
	Farm D	0.5 (0.22 - 1.12)	
	BCS1 ¹ x LN	1.06 (0.87 - 1.29)	<i>P</i> = 0.58 <i>ns</i> ⁵
2 (1425)	BCS2 ²	1.15 (0.83 - 1.6)	<i>P</i> = 0.4 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lactation Number	0.87 (0.6 - 1.26)	<i>P</i> = 0.46 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lame	0.65 (0.57 - 0.77)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm A	0.84 (0.49 - 1.43)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm B	1.3 (0.77 - 2.22)	
	Farm C	1.11 (0.65 - 1.89)	
	Farm D	0.74 (0.43 - 1.29)	
	BCS2 ² x LN	1.07 (0.95 - 1.21)	<i>P</i> = 0.28 <i>ns</i> ⁵
3 (777)	(BCS2-BCS1)	1.01 (0.4 - 2.55)	<i>P</i> = 0.99 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.02 (0.96 - 1.09)	<i>P</i> = 0.49 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lame	0.64 (0.53 - 0.78)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm A	0.59 (0.28 - 1.26)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm B	0.86 (0.4 - 1.83)	
	Farm C	2.03 (0.96 - 4.3)	
	Farm D	0.52 (0.24 - 1.13)	
	(BCS2-BCS1) x LN	1.2 (0.85 - 1.69)	<i>P</i> = 0.31 <i>ns</i> ⁵
4 (1425)	dBCS ³	1.14 (0.72 - 1.82)	<i>P</i> = 0.57 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.04 (0.98 - 1.1)	<i>P</i> = 0.24 <i>ns</i> ⁵
	Lame	0.64 (0.55 - 0.74)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm A	0.85 (0.5 - 1.43)	<i>P</i> <0.001
	Farm B	1.34 (0.79 - 2.28)	
	Farm C	1.09 (0.64 - 1.85)	
	Farm D	0.72 (0.42 - 1.25)	
	dBCS ³ x LN	1.06 (0.88 - 1.28)	<i>P</i> = 0.53 <i>ns</i> ⁵

⁵ *ns* = not statistically significant

¹ BCS1 = BCS at drying-off

² BCS2 = BCS at calving

³ dBCS = maximum BCS loss between calving & pregnancy

⁴ HR = Hazard Ratio (95% confidence interval)

Table S5: Analytical models to estimate the association between body condition score (BCS), lameness and time to pregnancy on four British dairy farms, adjusted for lactation number and for Farm as a random effect. Inseminated animals with an anticipated pregnancy test date after the end of the study are included.

Model # (n)	Predictor Variable	HR ⁴ (95% ci)	P-value
1 (883)	BCS1 ¹	1.12 (0.8 - 1.55)	<i>P</i> = 0.51 ns ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.01 (0.95 - 1.07)	<i>P</i> = 0.81 ns ⁵
	Lame	0.67 (0.55 - 0.81)	<i>P</i> < 0.001
	Farm	-	<i>P</i> < 0.001
2 (1,615)	BCS2 ²	1.23 (1.02 - 1.49)	<i>P</i> = 0.031
	Lactation Number	1.07 (1.02 - 1.11)	<i>P</i> = 0.003
	Lame	0.66 (0.57 - 0.77)	<i>P</i> < 0.001
	Farm	-	<i>P</i> < 0.001
3 (883)	(BCS2-BCS1)	1.57 (0.99 - 2.49)	<i>P</i> = 0.054 ns ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.01 (0.95 - 1.07)	<i>P</i> = 0.63 ns ⁵
	Lame	0.65 (0.54 - 0.79)	<i>P</i> < 0.001
	Farm	-	<i>P</i> < 0.001
4 (1,615)	dBCS ³	1.1 (0.83 - 1.46)	<i>P</i> = 0.49 ns ⁵
	Lactation Number	1.06 (1.01 - 1.1)	<i>P</i> = 0.012
	Lame	0.65 (0.56 - 0.76)	<i>P</i> < 0.001
	Farm	-	<i>P</i> < 0.001

¹ BCS1 = BCS at drying-off

² BCS2 = BCS at calving

³ dBCS = maximum BCS loss in calving-pregnancy interval (CPI)

⁴ HR = Hazard Ratio (95% confidence interval)

⁵ ns = not statistically significant

Figure S1: Pairwise correlations between measures of Body Condition Score (BCS) for cows on four British dairy farms (BCS1 is at drying-off; BCS2 is at calving; dBCS is maximum loss in BCS between calving and pregnancy).

Figure S1A: Correlation between BCS1 and BCS2

Figure S1B: Correlation between BCS1 and dBCS

Figure S1C: Correlation between BCS2 and dBCS

Figure S1D: Correlation between BCS1 and (BCS1-BCS2)

Figure S1E: Correlation between dBCS and (BCS2-BCS1)

Figure S2: Scatter plots of residuals compared to BCS variables for four Cox proportional hazard models estimating the associations between calving-pregnancy interval (CPI), BCS, and lameness adjusted for lactation number and farm.

Figure S2A: BCS1

Figure S2B: BCS2

Figure S2C: (BCS2-BCS1)

Figure S2D: dBCS

Figure S3: Deviance Residuals plots for four Cox proportional hazard models estimating the associations between calving-pregnancy interval (CPI), BCS, and lameness adjusted for lactation number and farm.

Figure S3A: Model 1 (BCS1)

Figure S3B: Model 2 (BCS2)

Figure S3C: Model 3 (BCS2-BCS1)

Figure S3D: Model 4 dBCS

Figure S4 Survival curves showing the proportion of animals not pregnant over time grouped by age (lactation number), adjusted for BCS or change in BCS for cows on four British dairy farms.

Figure S4A: BCS1

Figure S4B: BCS2

Figure S4C: BCS2-BCS1

Figure S4D: dBCS

Figure S5: Survival curves showing the proportion of animals not pregnant over time grouped by lameness status, adjusted for BCS or change in BCS for cows on four British dairy farms.

Figure S5A: BCS1

Figure S5B: BCS2

Figure S5C: BCS2-BCS1

Figure S5D: dBCS

Figure S6: Proportion of cows from four British dairy farms that were not pregnant by lameness status and adjusted for BCS or change in BCS at 75, 100, 125 or 150 days after calving.

Figure S6A: BCS1

Figure S6B: BCS2

Figure S6C: BCS2-BCS1

Figure S6D: dBCS